

The Zincke-Suhl Reaction

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THE Zincke-Suhl reaction¹, which is named after the authors, involves the reaction between p-cresol and carbon tetrachloride to yield 4-methyl-4-trichloromethyl-2,5-cyclohexadienone (II).

In this procedure, aluminium chloride is added to a solution of p-cresol in carbon tetrachloride. After a period of heating, the product II is isolated by hydrolysing the reaction mixture. By a proper choice of conditions the dienone II can be obtained in about 56% yield².

The Zincke-Suhl reaction to prepare the cyclohexadienone derivatives affords a possible general method for synthesising compounds containing a quaternary carbon atom and the cyclohexadienones have been shown to undergo many interesting reactions³.

The chemistry of these cyclohexadienones was first studied and many of their remarkable properties observed by Auwers and collaborators^{3a,4,5,6}. Subsequently, the establishment of the presence of a cyclohexadienone ring in the natural product santonin⁷ and the use of the cyclohexadienone intermediates in the aromatization of the ring A of the sterol nucleus⁸ engendered renewed interest in the chemical properties

of cyclohexadienones and in methods for their synthesis.

Although the chemistry of 4-methyl-4-dichloromethyl-2,5-cyclohexadienone (III), and other abnormal Reimer-Tiemann reaction products has been studied in great detail by Auwers and collaborators,^{5,6} only one paper on the chemistry of 4-methyl-4-trichloromethyl-2,5-cyclohexadienone (II) has appeared from that laboratory in 1922^{3a}. Since then no work was reported on the subject till about 1954². In recent years a number of papers on the subject have been published^{3b,e}.

The work on the study of the Zincke-Suhl reaction to yield the cyclohexadienones was undertaken in our laboratory with a view to studying the scope and the general applicability of the reaction for the following reasons :

(1) 4-Alkyl-4-trihalogenomethyl-2,5-cyclohexadienones formed in the reaction are very useful compounds and react with a variety of reagents^{3a-e} to yield compounds which are not easily accessible by other methods of synthesis.

(2) There is a possibility of utilizing the above reaction for the introduction of an angular di- or trihalogeno-methyl group into certain nuclei⁹.

It might be mentioned that 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-naphthol (IV) when subjected to a Reimer-Tiemann reaction has been found by Woodward⁹ to yield a dichloromethyl derivative (V) which was converted by him to trans-10-methyldecalone-2 (VI).

Wenkert and Stevens¹⁰ prepared a hexahydro-phenanthrene (VIII) possessing the natural A'B ring fusion of aromatic tricyclic diterpenes from 4-dichloromethyl-4-methyl-1 (4H)-naphthalenone (VII). The latter was obtained by the Reimer-Tiemann reaction of 4-methyl-1-naphthol.

(3) The cyclohexanones formed by the hydrogenation of cyclohexadienones are of pharmacological interest and are reported to show considerable anthelmintic activity to eel-worm infestation in pups¹¹.

The general applicability of the Zincke-Suhl reaction has been investigated by us¹² by using a number of substituted p-alkyl phenols, varying the conditions of the reaction and by employing other alkyl halides in place of carbon tetrachloride.

In a comparative study made by using p-cresol, 3, 4-dimethylphenol and 3, 4, 5-trimethylphenol under Zincke-Suhl reaction conditions, it was found^{9e} that as the methyl substitution at positions meta to the phenolic group increased, the optimum temperatures fell, the reaction time increased and the amounts of tars formed in the reaction decreased.

It has been observed^{12a} that as the alkyl group becomes bulky, the yield of cyclohexadienone goes on decreasing and p-hydroxybiphenyl, p-hydroxydiphenylmethane and p-cyclohexylphenol do not take part in the reaction. It is also found that 2, 4, 6-trimethylphenol does not undergo the Zincke-Suhl reaction probably due to the steric hindrance of the methyl group next to the hydroxyl.

In the naphthalene series, 4-methyl-1-naphthol under the conditions of the Zincke-Suhl reaction yielded 4-methyl-4-trichloromethyl-1-(4H)-naphthalenone^{12b}.

4-Ethyl-1-naphthol instead of the desired naphthalenone, gave a ketone not containing any halogen¹⁷. The spectral data indicated the compound to be a tetralone derivative. It is not clearly understood how this is formed.¹³

Further, when the Zincke-Suhl reaction was applied to 4-methyl-1-anthrol, instead of the expected cyclohexadienone a crystalline compound free from halogen was isolated.¹³

A theory with regard to the mechanism of the Zincke-Suhl reaction has been postulated² according to which aluminium chloride plays a dual role. It first reacts with p-cresol to form a chloroaluminium salt (IX) as shown below :

The chloride ion displaced, combines with the AlCl_2^+ ion to produce aluminium chloride which remains complexed with the product (XI).

The salt (IX A) may react at three positions : the reaction at p-carbon atom '1' gives the dienone II, at the o-carbon atom '2' it yields products which eventually lead to polymers formed in the reaction, and that at the oxygen '3' yields carbonates which have been isolated previously, when 2, 3, 5, 6-tetra-bromo-p-cresol was employed in the reaction¹. It has been found by us that both carbon tetrabromide and bromoform can be used in the Zincke-Suhl reaction to yield the corresponding cyclohexadienone derivatives provided anhydrous aluminium bromide is used in the reaction¹². Also, it has been noticed that both carbontetraiodide and iodoform in the presence of anhydrous aluminium iodide fail to give the corresponding cyclohexadienones¹³.

Further, chloroform, acetylene tetrachloride and hexachloroethane do not take part in this reaction.

During the work on the Zincke-Suhl reaction with different p-alkyl-phenols several surprising results were encountered : (a) 2, 6-di-t-butyl-p-cresol when treated with a carbon tetrahalide in the presence of the appropriate anhydrous aluminium halide, underwent the reaction with the elimination of both the t-butyl groups to give 4-methyl-4-trihalogenomethyl-2, 5-cyclohexadienone ; (b) 2-methoxy-4-methylphenol yielded, instead of the expected cyclohexadienone derivative, 2, 2'-dihydroxy - 3, 3'- dimethoxy - 5, 5'-dimethylbenzophenone whilst 4-chloro-2, 3'-dimethyl-6'-hydroxybenzophenone resulted when p-cresol was reacted with 4-chloro-2-methylbenzotrichloride. Also, the reaction between 3, 4-dimethylphenol and carbon tetrabromide when carried out at 0-5° afforded besides the expected dienone, a benzophenone derivative viz 2, 2'-dihydroxy-4, 4', 5, 5'-tetramethyl-benzophenone ; when the reaction was carried out at 40-45°, only a small amount of 3, 4-dimethyl-6-hydroxybenzoic acid was obtained to the entire exclusion of the dienone or the benzophenone derivative. The formation of the benzophenone derivative is explained as indicated.

The cyclohexadienone derivatives which were either solids or oils showed the characteristic carbonyl absorption in both the uv and ir absorption spectra, gave 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, oximes and semicarbozones and evolved hydrogen chloride or bromide when treated with concentrated sulfuric acid. A 10% alkaline solution had no effect on the dienones at room temperature. However, on boiling the dienones with alkali, dark tars were obtained from which no definite product could be isolated.

It is beyond the scope of this article to enumerate all the interesting reactions which these cyclohexadienone derivative undergo. However, some of the important reactions are described below :

Action of Phosphorus pentachloride or Pentabromide :

Treatment of the cyclohexadienone derivatives with phosphorus penta halides induced migrations of the 4-methyl or 4-trihalogenomethyl group depending upon the structure of the dienone derivative, resulting in the aromatization of the nucleus^{3a,c}. For example, the dienone II when treated with phosphorus pentachloride gave 4-chloro-2-methylbenzotrichloride which was converted to 4-chloro-2-methylbenzoic acid^{3a}. However, the dienone XII gave 4-methyl-3-(β, β, β-trichloroethyl)-chlorobenzene(XIII)^{3e}. The tribromomethyl-cyclohexadienone derivatives under-go precisely the same type of rearrangements¹² with phosphorus pentabromide.

The formation of 4-chloro-2-methylbenzoic acid and 4-methyl-3-(β, β, β-trichloroethyl)-chlorobenzene (XIII) can be explained as shown.

It is of interest to note that 4-methyl-4-dichloromethyl-2, 5-cyclohexadienone (III) when treated with phosphorus pentachloride was found to yield 4-chloro-2-methylbenzaldehyde⁵.

In another experiment, when the dienone XIV was treated with phosphorus pentachloride, 3-chloro-2, 6-dimethylbenzoic acid (XV) was obtained¹². This appears to be the first known case of a 1:2 migration of trichloromethyl group.

The results of the phosphorus pentachloride reaction on the higher derivatives, viz., 4-ethyl, 4-propyl and 4-butyl-4-trichloromethyl 2, 5-cyclohexadienones were very surprising, for in each case, besides 2-alkyl-4-chlorobenzoic acid, the normal rearrangement product, p-chlorobenzoic acid was a common product.

Action of Polyphosphoric Acid (PPA)

While the dienone II when treated with polyphosphoric acid afforded 4-chloro-2-methylbenzoic acid and p-chlorotoluene, (the tribromodienone undergoes similar rearrangement), the dienone XII afforded, besides 3, 4-dimethylchlorobenzene (XVI), two isomeric acids (XVII and XVIII)^{3b}.

The mechanism for the formation of the above product is shown below :

Action of Sulfuric Acid

The dienone III was observed to yield 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-benzaldehyde, when treated with 80% sulfuric acid accompanied by the unchanged dienone and some dye¹⁴. However, the dienone II rearranged completely to yield a mixture of m-cresol sulfonic acid, 3-sulfo-2, 5-cresotic acid and small amounts of 2, 5-cresotic acid¹⁴. 4-Methyl-4-tribromomethyl-2, 5-cyclohexadienone (XIX) when treated with 80% sulfuric acid at 90-95° for 24 hr. gave a mixture of 4-methyl-2, 3, 6-tribromophenol (XX), 3, 5-dibromo-4-hydroxy-2-methylbenzoic acid (XXI) and 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzoic acid (XXII)¹².

The mechanism for the formation of the products XX, XXI and XXII is not very clear.

Action of Acetic Anhydride

The dienones II, III and XIX failed to rearrange when treated with a catalytic amount of sulfuric acid in acetic anhydride, a medium which serves well for similar unchlorinated compounds.¹⁵ However, the dienone XII could be converted, by prolonged boiling of its acetic anhydride solution containing a small amount of sulfuric acid or hydrogen chloride to 4-methyl-3-β, β, β-trichloroethyl-phenyl acetate

(XXIII) in excellent yields^{3d}. When the dienone XII was heated with aroyl chlorides under the above conditions, acyl derivatives corresponding to XXIII were obtained^{3d}. However, both 4-methyl-4-trichloromethyl-2, 5-cyclohexadienone (II) and 4-methyl-4-tribromomethyl-2, 5-cyclohexadienone (XIX) failed to take part in the above reaction.

Action of the Grignard Reagent and Lithium Aluminium Hydride

The dienone II was converted to the corresponding carbinol XXIV by the action of methyl magnesium iodide^{3a}. The latter as a rule, changes after a few

hours with violent ebullition, through the labile semi-benzene into α-(p-tolyl)-β, β, β-trichloroethane (XXV). The dienone II when treated with phenylmagnesium bromide yielded the carbinol XXVI which when treated with 90% formic acid yielded a mixture containing p-methylbiphenyl (XXVII), 3-methyl-4-trichloromethylbiphenyl (XXVIII) and 2-methyl-4-phenylbenzoic acid (XXIX)^{3e}. However, the dienone XII when treated with phenyl-, methyl- and ethoxyethyl-magnesium bromides failed to give the expected carbinols since rearrangements of the trichloromethyl group occurred even under mild conditions.^{3e}

The dienone II was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride in ether solution to give the corresponding alcohol¹⁶.

Hydrogenation of Cyclohexadienones

Through hydrogenation of the cyclohexadienone derivatives, a series of cyclohexanones and cyclohexenones was prepared leading to alternative methods to 2, 4, 4-trimethyl-2-cyclohexenone and 2, 4, 4-trimethyl-2, 5-cyclohexenone.¹¹ The latter showed considerable anthelmintic activity to eel-worm (*Ascaris lumbricoides*) infestation in pups. Also, the hydrogenation of substituted cyclohexadienone derivatives gives stereoisomers the study of which has attracted considerable attention¹¹. It is possible to replace the -CCl₃ by CH₃ group in II by catalytic hydrogenation under special conditions^{11a}.

Rearrangement of the Oximes of Cyclohexadienones :

Oxime of cyclohexadienone III when treated with 4% NaOH under nitrogen atmosphere was transformed into 4-methyltropone oxime (XXX)¹⁷.

However, it has been observed by us, that under similar conditions 4 methyl-4-trichloromethyl-2, 5-cyclohexadienone (II) and 4-methyl-4-tribromome-

thyl-2, 5-cyclohexadienone (XIX) yield 3-chloro-p-toluic acid and 3-bromo-p-toluic acid respectively.^{12a}

Schiff's bases from Cyclohexadienones :

Cyclohexadienone III with alkylamines, cyclohexylamine and butylamine gives Schiff's bases¹⁸.

During the preparation of a number of these it was observed that o-substituted amines do not give these bases as well as di- and tri-substituted cyclohexadienones also were unreactive¹³.

When the Schiff's base, obtained by the reaction of cyclohexadienone II with aniline was further heated with aniline, N-phenyl-p-toluidine and 4-aminobenzoic acid-(N, N'-diphenylamidine) resulted.

The above reactions of the cyclohexadienone derivatives show their versatility. Most of the reactions are accompanied by the aromatization of the ring and migration of the groups from 'p' carbon atom. This property has been made use of in the steroid field.

During the synthesis of the 2-oxaadamantane ring system Stetter and Mayer¹⁹ condensed cyclohexadienone III with acetonedicarboxylic acid dimethyl ester in the presence of sodium methoxide to yield di-me-9-methyl-9-dichloromethyl-bicyclo-3, 3, 1-nonane-3, 7-dione-2, 4-dicarboxylate (XXXI).

However, instead of product XXXI another compound which does not contain halogen was obtained by us. From the spectral data the latter was found to be the orthoester XXXII.

Recently, the irradiation of this cyclohexadienone II has been reported to give a 5-hydroxycyclopentanone derivative²¹.

Thus it can be seen that the Zincke-Suhl reaction is a valuable tool in the hands of organic chemists as it yields cyclohexadienone derivatives which are very versatile compounds capable of undergoing a number of interesting reactions.

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